

ACTIVE AGEING FOR CULTURAL SERVICES: FOCUS ON ELDERLY POPULATION IN INLAND AREAS

Giovanna Del Gobbo^a

Sofia Marconi^a

Cristina Banchi^a

Giulia Biagi^a

Francesco De Maria^a

^aUniversity of Florence

In the last twenty years, the concept of local heritage has changed and expanded, with a general convergence towards the unity of natural, cultural and social dimensions (Del Gobbo & Galeotti, 2018). The current debate also confirms the shift towards people-centred approaches (Auclair & Fairclough, 2015), suggesting a focus on bottom-up processes in cultural policy and heritage governance, involving diverse stakeholders and dynamic networks for heritage management and use. This paradigm shift influences the day-to-day activities of cultural institutions and third sector actors providing access to, use and preservation of local heritage (UN, 2022; Gordon & Beilby-Orrin, 2007). This article presents the results of a pilot study conducted in the Casentino valley, a mountainous region in the centre of Tuscany with a high age index. A mixed methods approach was used to identify the active participation of the over 55s in the provision of cultural services and the benefits of active ageing through the enjoyment and use of cultural heritage. The study is original in it aims to highlight the fundamental role of the older population in ensuring access to and use of cultural heritage by tapping the potential for informal and non-formal education opportunities.

active ageing; cultural heritage; community wellbeing; ecosystem services; inland areas

INTRODUCTION

This paper presents the results of a study carried out in the mountainous region of Casentino in Tuscany (Italy), focusing on the active participation of the over

55s in the provision of cultural services. In particular, it examined the extent to which cultural heritage valorization activities promote active ageing among the over 55s and to which these individuals, generally acting within local cultural associations, foster a knowledge of the values and traditions of the mountainous region in which they live.

The literature points out that volunteering, in this case in the cultural sphere, contributes to the sustainability and well-being of local communities (Zaidi & Stanton, 2015). Therefore, volunteering can also be associated with favorable processes of active ageing in territories where it is practised and widespread (Boerio et al., 2023; Jongenelis et al., 2022). Active ageing refers to a category based on three pillars, as proposed by the Active Ageing Index¹: health, participation and security. Cultural volunteering and related activities promote the well-being of the over-55s, while volunteers' participation in the local community strengthens and defines their role. The creation of solidarity networks through the mechanism of volunteering not only combats ageism² but also creates social security, especially when supported by inclusive measures (Zaidi & Stanton, 2015).

In the case in point, mediated by associations active in the territories and their volunteers, cultural heritage promotes active ageing processes, playing an intrinsic educational role, and promotes the development of social skills and competences such as critical action, greater autonomy, self-control and empowerment (Marconi, 2024; Fancourt & Finn, 2019). Participation in heritage-related activities promotes overall social wellbeing, particularly among the over 55s, and improves cognition, the quality and quantity of relationships, and a sense of closeness and belonging (Bone & Fancourt, 2022; Goulding, 2018; Dadswell et al., 2017).

The approaches outlined above see cultural heritage as a valuable resource for active ageing, the well-being of individuals and local communities. They refer to models that are people-centred and not just about heritage preservation (Auclair & Fairclough, 2015), and are thus able to incorporate intangible, natural and social aspects alongside tangible ones (Del Gobbo & Galeotti, 2018) by adopting a holistic perspective (Del Gobbo et al., 2018).

In particular, the epistemological approach of ecosystem services, which was used as a reference for the present study, emphasises the fact that culture and

¹ <https://unece.org/population/active-ageing-index>

² According to the World Health Organisation (WHO), ageism refers to stereotypes (the way we think), prejudice (the way we feel) and discrimination (the way we act) against others or ourselves on the basis of age.

cultural activities can be considered as community services that generate non-material benefits, such as learning or spiritual enrichment, and contribute to the overall well-being and development of individuals and communities (MA, 2005). At the same time, the theoretical approaches described encourage a rethinking of cultural heritage management. Only through the active involvement of different stakeholders of different ages and the existence of dynamic networks can local cultural heritage, with its specific characteristics and attributes, be managed effectively and sustainably.

1. BACKGROUND

The Casentino valley is a particular subject of the National Strategy for Inner Areas³ (S.N.A.I.) as it is a mountainous area at risk of marginalization. Specific funds are allocated to this territory for the improvement of services and the promotion of activities that can improve the local economy. Despite the phenomenon of depopulation and demographic ageing, the Third Sector and local associations are active in Casentino, with a total of 154 organizations registered in the Third Sector Single National Register⁴ (RUNTS), offering informal and non-formal learning opportunities.

2. RESEARCH QUESTIONS

The hypothesis underlying the present research in Casentino is that the cultural third sector fosters processes to improve social capital and community well-being (Atkinson, et al., 2017), being able to nurture social relations, create or improve territorial services and promote active citizenship (UN, 2022; Krlev et al., 2021). In particular, volunteers over the age of 55 engaged in cultural associations in Casentino give their time and knowledge to their local community and are important actors in the processes of transmission, hybridization and cultural creativity that can emerge in territories, especially in mountainous areas (Viazzo & Zanini, 2014). The questions guiding the research were twofold: 1) Do the over 55s in Casentino play a role as producers of cultural services, and do they promote access to and the dynamic preservation of the region's cultural heritage? 2) Is there a recognizable relationship between

³ <https://politichecoesione.governo.it/it/politica-di-coesione/strategie-tematiche-e-territoriali/strategie-territoriali/strategia-nazionale-aree-interne-snai/>

⁴ The Third Sector Single National Register (RUNTS) is a tool to get to know non-profit organisations, containing basic information about the characteristics of registered organisations, further to Article 45 of the Law on the Third Sector (Legislative Decree No. 117 of 3 July 2017)

cultural volunteering and active ageing?

3. METHODOLOGY

Case study. The research design used to investigate the relationship between the over 55s, active ageing and cultural heritage is qualitative-quantitative (mixed and multi methods), correlative and observational, with an exploratory objective to describe and interpret an ongoing phenomenon that has been little studied from an empirical point of view. What is described in the article is a digital form that was created with a set of survey dimensions that could be freely compiled by the contact persons of the cultural associations surveyed. The main dimensions of the organizations surveyed were: the type of activities carried out; the number of people active in the organization; the youngest, oldest and average age of people active in the organization; the ageing of the population and strategies for generational change.

3.1. Convenience Sampling

Between March and May 2024, 154 associations in the Casentino region were identified via the Third Sector Single National Register (RUNTS). Of these, 38 were contacted, as they could be categorized as cultural. During the contact process 5 organizations could not be contacted, while 33 associations confirmed their willingness to participate in the study. In the end, 27 associations actually took part in the survey, with 26 cultural organizations returning the completed form by e-mail and one organization preferring to submit their data by telephone.

4. RESULTS

The data on the 27 participating associations provided useful information on the type of cultural activities and services promoted by the different organizations surveyed, as well as on the profile of their members. The six main areas of activity of the cultural associations appear to be archaeological and historical research, organization of exhibitions and festivals, management of libraries and craft workshops, maintenance of village decorum, promotion of tourism and food culture, and promotion of sporting activities. The cultural associations in Casentino that took part in the survey have a total of 1988 members, 1021 of whom are volunteers. The average age of members is 60, with a top age of 90 and a low of 6. The spokespersons of the associations interviewed stated that the over 55s are very much involved in the proposed activities, in terms of

organization, leadership and commitment to the region, and that these people have strong ethical and civic values. Furthermore, 20 of the 27 respondents believe that the progressive ageing of the population in Casentino threatens the sustainability of the cultural activities they currently propose in the territory. In particular, four associations are very concerned that without a generational change, they will close within a few years, which could have a negative impact on the cultural heritage of Casentino. To address this issue, 17 of the 20 associations state that they have already launched initiatives to involve young people more in Casentino, although the results of these strategies cannot yet be assessed. Youth participation seems to be crucial for the operational sustainability of the cultural associations surveyed.

5. CONCLUSIONS

The strong presence of the over 55s in the various cultural activities promoted by the cultural associations surveyed in Casentino emphasises their important role as producers of cultural services and as a source of experience and knowledge. The lack of specific and wide-ranging initiatives to address the impending impossibility for the older population of Casentino to continue to provide many cultural services in the area and to actively involve younger generations represents a major challenge for Casentino and its cultural heritage. This area is facing a profound demographic, social and cultural shake-up. Currently, a significant proportion of the cultural associations interviewed in the study are kept alive by mostly older members who are only sporadically able to create synergies and collaborate with younger people.

The study also highlighted the strong values and solidarity among the over 55s. In addition to their role in the region's cultural associations, they also benefit from cultural activities as a way to stay active. This suggests that cultural associations can serve as a platform for intergenerational processes (Baschiera, 2013), for inclusion and for the creation of a safe and cohesive social environment for the over 55s and, more generally, for the entire local community. Despite the challenges for the Casentino valley related to the ageing of the population and the management and sustainability of the cultural services currently in place, we emphasise the fact that this territory is characterized by a diverse and vibrant panorama of cultural projects and research initiatives. It is therefore possible and desirable that ongoing social and cultural transformations are able to create "empty" spaces (Viazzo & Zanini, 2014) from which creativity and cultural innovation can emerge.

Acknowledgements

We wish to acknowledge the contributions of all participants in the working group of the research “REACT. Regenerating the cultural landscapes of inland areas in a people-centered perspective” CUP B55F21007810001, funded by the Next Generation EU and the Italian National Research Programme (NRP) 2021-2027, to the results presented in this paper. We also wish to acknowledge co-funding from Next Generation EU, in the context of the National Recovery and Resilience Plan, M4C2 Investment 1.3: •PE_0000015, PE8, Age-It – A novel public-private alliance to generate socioeconomic, biomedical and technological solutions for an inclusive Italian ageing society. CUP B83C22004800006 •PE_0000020, PE5, CHANGES, Cultural Heritage Active Innovation for Sustainable Society. CUP: B53C22004010006. This resource was co-financed by the Next Generation EU. The views and opinions expressed are only those of the authors and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Commission. Neither the European Union nor the European Commission can be held responsible for them.

REFERENCES

- Atkinson, S., Bagnall, A.M., Corcoran, R., South, J., Curtis, S., Di Martino, S., & Pilkington, G. (2017). *What is community wellbeing? Conceptual Review*. What Works Wellbeing.
- Auclair, E., & Fairclough, G. (2015). *Theory and practice in heritage and sustainability: Between past and future*. Routledge.
- Baschiera, B. (2013). *Le relazioni intergenerazionali e la coesione sociale. La voce degli anziani e dei giovani*. FrancoAngeli.
- Boerio, P., Garavaglia, E., & Gaia, A. (2023). Active ageing in Europe. Are changes in social capital associated with engagement, initiation, and maintenance of activity in later life?. *Ageing & Society*, 43, 1122–1140. doi:10.1017/S0144686X21001021
- Bone, J. K., & Fancourt, D. (2022). The impact of social and cultural activities on the mental health of older adults in the UK. *BMC Geriatrics*, 22(1), 1-10.
- Dadswell, A., Wilson, C., Bungay, H., & Munn-Giddings, C. (2017). The role of participatory arts in addressing the loneliness and social isolation of older people: A conceptual review of the literature. *Journal of Arts & Communities*, 9(2), pp. 109–28.
- Del Gobbo G., & Galeotti, G. (2018). Natural and cultural capitals: transdisciplinary strategies toward community learning for sustainable and inclusive human development. In Paracchini, M. L., Zingari, P. C., & Blasi, C. (edited

- by). *Reconnecting Natural and Cultural Capital. Contributions from Science and Policy* (pp. 163-174). Publications Office of the European Union.
- Del Gobbo G., Torlone, F. & Galeotti, G. (2018). Le valenze educative del patrimonio culturale. Riflessioni teorico-metodologiche tra ricerca evidence-based e azione educativa nei musei. Aracne.
- Fancourt, D., & Finn, S. (2019). *What is the evidence on the role of the arts in improving health and well-being? A scoping review*. WHO Regional Office for Europe. Health Evidence Network (HEN). Synthesis Report 67.
- Gordon, J. C., & Beilby-Orrin, H. (2007). *International Measurement of the Economic and Social Importance of Culture*. OECD Statistics Working Papers. <https://doi.org/10.1787/5k92znx7sc30-en>
- Goulding, A. (2018). The Role of Cultural Engagement in Older People's Lives. *Cultural Sociology*, 12(4), 518-539. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1749975518754461>
- Jongenelis, M., Jackson, B., Newton, R.U., & Pettigrew, S. (2022). Longitudinal associations between formal volunteering and well-being among retired older people. *Ageing and Mental Health*, vol.26. DOI: <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/13607863.2021.1884845>.
- Krlev, G., Pasi, G., Wruk, D., & Bernhard, M. (2021). *Reconceptualizing the Social Economy*. Stanford Social Innovation Review. Stanford University. DOI: 10.48558/98vt-g859. https://ssir.org/articles/entry/reconceptualizing_the_social_economy
- Marconi, S. (2024). "Stare bene", insieme. Il dispositivo patrimonio culturale per il benessere comunitario. In Boffo, V., Del Gobbo, G., Malavasi, P. (a cura di). *Dare la parola: professionalità pedagogiche, educative e formative. A 100 anni dalla nascita di Don Milani*. (pp. 654-659). Pensa Multimedia.
- Millennium Ecosystem Assessment. (2005). *Ecosystems and human well-being: Synthesis*. Island Press.
- UN. (2022). Position Paper of the United Nations Inter-Agency Task Force on Social and Solidarity Economy. Advancing the 2030 Agenda through the Social and Solidarity Economy.
- Viazzo, P. P., & Zanini, R. C. (2014). "Approfittare del vuoto"? Prospettive antropologiche su neo-popolamento e spazi di creatività culturale in area alpina". *Journal of Alpine Research | Revue de géographie alpine*, n° 102(3). <https://doi.org/10.4000/rga.2476>.
- Zaidi, A., & Stanton, D. (2015). *Active Ageing Index 2014. Analytical Report*. UNECE/European Commission. Directorate General for Employment,

Social Affairs and Inclusion. https://www.southampton.ac.uk/~assets/doc/aai_report.pdf